

2LEAD: A COMPACT LIBS INSTRUMENT FOR IN-SITU ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF LUNAR SURFACE MATERIALS. J. J. Gillis¹, N. D. S. Webb¹, F. Rehnmark², R. Blanco³, A. Hickman³, ¹Washington University, One Brookings Drive, Dept. of Physics, St. Louis MO, 63130 USA (j.gillis@wustl.edu), ²S&B Precision Machines Consulting, 7 Peachtree Lane, Ithaca, New York 14850, USA. ³AVS US, 126 Ridge Rd, Lansing, New York 14882, USA

Introduction: Understanding the compositional diversity of lunar surface materials is essential for reconstructing the Moon's geologic history, assessing volatile inventories, and supporting future exploration activities. Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) is a particularly attractive technique for lunar exploration because it enables rapid, stand-off, multi-element compositional analysis without sample preparation. In particular, the identification of evolved igneous materials, regolith evolution, and volatile-associated processes on the Moon has emerged as a key scientific objective in recent years. These topics are directly relevant to ongoing international lunar exploration efforts, including NASA's Artemis program and the growing participation of European institutions in robotic and human exploration initiatives.

We are developing 2LEAD (Lunar-LIBS Elemental Analysis and Detection), a compact LIBS instrument for deployment on small lunar landers, rovers, and hoppers (**Fig. 1**). Currently at TRL-5 under NASA's Development and Advancement of Lunar Instrumentation (DALI) program, 2LEAD is entering its engineering model build and environmental test campaign, on track to achieve TRL-6 by early 2027. 2LEAD is designed to provide quantitative measurements of major rock-forming elements including Si, Fe, Al, Mg, Ti, Ca, and K, enabling identification of lunar lithologies.

One potential scientific use for 2LEAD is to investigate the Compton-Belkovich Volcanic Complex (CBVC). CBVC represents one of the Moon's most unusual volcanic provinces, characterized by high thorium concentrations, silicic volcanism, and morphologies consistent with explosive eruptions. In-situ geochemical measurements are critical to determining whether CBVC represents evolved silicic volcanism, volatile-driven explosive activity, or another form of unusual lunar magmatism.

Background: LIBS uses a pulsed laser focused on the target surface generates a micro-plasma that emits characteristic atomic emission lines. These emission lines are analyzed spectroscopically to determine elemental composition.

Our instrument builds on 10+ years of Mars LIBS science (ChemCam [1], SuperCam [2], MarSCoDe [3]), and demonstration of LIBS under lunar-like vacuum conditions [4-10] and on the lunar surface (Chandrayaan-3 [11]). For lunar science, LIBS measurements provide important constraints on igneous processes, crustal composition, and regolith evolution. In addition, elemental ratios such as Mg/Al, Fe/Al, and Si/Al can be used to identify major lithologies and

investigate magmatic differentiation. 2LEAD will also inform future exploration and utilization through measuring the abundance of H₂O/OH, LIBS can measure H₂O to a limit of detection around 0.4 wt% [12]. These measurements also provide valuable ground truth for orbital remote-sensing observations.

2LEAD: The LIBS instrument architecture consists of an internal body unit that contains a two-channel spectrometer, a ~10–50 mJ, 1,064 nm, pulsed laser with pulse width of 6–7 ns, context camera, and scanning and focus optics that acquire the sampling target. The laser, spectrometer, and camera are all aligned to a common optical path through the focus and scan subassembly so that when the camera image of a Region Of Interest (ROI) on the sampling target is brought into focus, the laser and spectrometer are both also focused at the same spot. Plasma light generated by the laser is transmitted through the scanning mirror, focusing lenses, and redirected directly in the dual spectrometers.

The wavelength and intensity of the emission peaks is measured by the spectrometer (180–840 nm with resolution of 0.6 nm). This design provides excellent measurement sensitivity in the shorter UV wavelengths relevant to the science objective.

2LEAD has focusable optics from 0.5–2.0 m, which collect clearly distinguishable spectra at high (10⁻⁶ mbar) vacuum (**Fig. 2**). It is typically hypothesized that the LIBS plasma in experimental conditions at 10⁻⁴ mbar will behave similarly to a real LIBS plasma on the surface of the Moon, where the pressure is much lower [13].

In contrast to a mast-mounted unit (such as SuperCam and ChemCam on Mars) with a motorized gimbal that provides the capability to point the instrument at targets of interest, the 2LEAD is rigidly mounted on the front of the rover with a window angled down ~30° below horizontal (**Fig. 1**). An internal beam

Fig 1. 2LEAD mounted on a CLPS-style rover. Vectors show its range of motion at a 1m standoff.

steering mirror gives the instrument a scanning envelope of ± 12 degrees, enough to reach a 40×40 cm sampling grid at 1m standoff from science targets encountered on the surface. Optical elements are selected assuming a hypothetical payload mounting height of 0.5 m from the surface. Straightforward modifications can be made to the instrument to adjust for alternate mounting provisions aboard different mobility platforms.

The LIBS Context camera will capture a “before” snapshot to document the intended spot and surrounding ROI, and an “after” image of the ablation pit to confirm the correct target was hit, surface alteration (darkening, dust blow-off) and the spatial footprint of shots, and if further shots should be placed on freshened material adjacent to the pit.

Conclusion: The 2LEAD instrument is being developed to provide a compact scanning standoff LIBS capability for future lunar surface exploration missions. 2LEAD can stand on its own or be combined in an instrument suite featuring multiple complementary measurements.

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Fig. 2. LIBS spectra of an anorthosite rock, showing prominent emission peaks for Fe, Ca, Al, Si, and Sr at 1-atm and vacuum ($1e^{-6}$ mbar). Inset shows context camera image showing multiple LIBS zap pits (white marks). 1mm ruler for scale. The image demonstrates that the camera resolves zap pits and different minerals, such that together with LIBS measurements, we can robustly identify which mineral was measured and assign it a unique chemical analysis.